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Pastoral Counselling: Panacea for the Divorce in the 21st Century Nigeria

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Abstract

One of the major institutions traceable to the early age of man and based on the Biblical narrative is the institution of marriage. It is not disputable that God instituted marriage from the inception of Adam and Eve which is seen in their union in the Garden of Eden. As such, Marriage in this context is based on the divinely ordained format of one man and one woman coming together in union to build a home. But as against the Biblical position and injunction on marriage which is to stand the test of time and to last "till death do us part", many homes in the 21st century have experienced serious hitches in the 'adventure' of marriage which have led to the threat of divorce in actual fact or in its potential form, divorce is almost the order of the day among many young couples in which there is a call for concern to remedy the situation. An examination of this status quo in Nigeria calls for immediate response and rescue mission. A chronicling of some practical instances and assessment of the response of the personalities involved in various situations which led to complications is the focal point in the course of this research work. Therefore, using the investigative method, this paper studies the major factors responsible for divorce in the 21st century among young and matured couples in Nigeria and the paper presents pastoral counselling in its true form as a panacea to rescue the situation of rampaging divorce in the contemporary age.

Keywords: Pastoral Counselling, Divorce, Marriage, Nigeria

Introduction

Marriage is God-ordained and the original intention and plan for marriage is that it serves "till death do the couple apart". But it appears that the contemporary time and situation of life have led to various complications in matters concerning marriage. Marriage is seen to be literally a contract without essential commitment to such contract, in recent times, marriage has loosed its sanctity because of the response of the people towards the practice among young and adult couples.

The modern days have seen various kind of unnatural marriages which ranges from getting married to the same sex, and marriage to animals among other kinds of marriages that are not part of the programming by God from the initials. The rampaging loss of the sanctity of marriage calls for intentional action and attention by the society as a whole, because the adverse

effect tells on the society as a whole. The neglect of the rampaging catastrophe in modern-day marriages which could be due to lack of cultural understanding and not being religiously inclined in a right way, has caused a lot of imbalances in the 21st century world.

To this existing marital malady, there is a need to seek escape route which this paper seeks to review the existing malady and with the discovery that there are a lot of gaps to be breached religiously in some of these situations, the pastoral counseling is seen as a means of calming the situation and to be seen as a remedy to the existing malady in the society

Concept of Pastoral Counselling

Pastoral counselling is a field that focuses on counsel for various issues of life. It is a special type of psychotherapy which promotes healing and growth with the use of both spiritual and psychological resources. The task is to be carried out by pastoral counsellors who are licensed and who have gone through a deep understanding in their Christian teachings and theologies, which will be also corroborated by their certification as mental health practitioners. Pastoral counselling utilises both spiritual resources and psychological analysis and approach to aid the healing process or growth of an individual. Their focus is basically to regulate extreme situations and to stabilise situations from escalating.

In order to promote therapeutic form and progress, pastoral counseling employs both psychological knowledge and spiritual resources. This is seen to be specifically a service or activities rendered by pastors, licensed to have received extensive religious and/or theological studies in addition to being mental health specialist. Challenging situations are bound to occur in lives and involvement of individuals; like mental disorder, overwhelming situations, family issues, child bearing challenges among others. In such season, they are advised to seek help and counsel in a way or the other. While some people will opt for psychologists, some will opt for social workers or psychiatrists, others will rather like to seek spiritual solutions in the context of their situation

Pastoral counselors are to be responsible for providing pastoral assistance, encouragement and the admonition to people who are bewildered or discouraged about various situations of life around them. They provide counsel for adults, children, adolescents, youths and even families. Their tasks also extend to providing assistance for people who are addicted to substances, or some involvements. Their task is encompassing and the goal is simply to bring sanctity into the society that they find themselves using religious, specifically biblical thoughts to encourage stability and progress for an individual or individuals.

The church is one of the most significant places where people seeking assistance visit, both when it deals with material things or when it has to do with the mental state of the individual either due to personal issues or issues from another party. People with depression, grief, sorrow, health challenges, societal imbalance, violence, especially in the African context believes that there is solution in the church and as such, pastoral counselling tend to be necessary to be applied to each situation which an individual encounters. It only becomes a challenge when most religious leaders, who people run to are not really trained in psychotherapy in order to aid extensive dealing with the challenge an individual must have brought to them to address. It therefore hinges that, pastors and church leaders are to be well trained in psychotherapy in

order to meet the actual need of some of this member especially when it comes to pastoral counselling.

The crux of pastoral counselling is to restore human back into the right relationship with God and to fellow humans which is not done without Christ in the course of the discourse. The pastoral counselling is an emerging academic discipline which creates a platform of operation for apologists from diverse faiths and religions to express their perspectives, with Jesus as a good model for pastoral counselling, the field is an emphatic delivery of biblical psychotherapy (Odeleye, 2022)

Techniques and Principles of Pastoral Counselling

As a discipline and as an upcoming field of emphasis, there are some major underlying principles, which guide the proper running of a pastoral counsellor. These principles present pastoral counselling to stand out from other genre of counselling in existence. These principles are discussed below;

First is the in-depth knowledge of the scriptures which is essential for the foundational basis of pastoral counselling. Having in mind that pastoral counselling as a field is spiritually inclined and based on the biblical positions in encouraging or counselling individuals in one challenge or the other. Odeleye (2022) reminded that the Scripture, which contains sixty-six books is the word of God and revelation from him, which is available to guide every aspect of Christian counselling. He further established that the Bible is sine-qua-non and applicable to any case or situation a man can find himself. It serves the purpose of guiding men and revealing the mind of God in various situations. Therefore, as pastoral counsellors, it is essential to have the knowledge of biblical injunctions as this will go a long way in aiding the rightful situating of the challenges of people and addressing it from the biblical perception.

Furthermore, in the techniques and principles of pastoral counselling is the lifestyle of prayer and meditation which ought to be possessed by pastoral counsellors. A pastoral counsellor is to be very sound in inculcating a life of prayer and meditation as this are fundamental to the sustainability of their roles as counsellors. Odeleye (2022) expressed that the hallmark through which a pastoral counsellor can operate is through communion and meditation with the Holy Spirit. Through a constant life of prayer and meditation, the counsellor comes up with revelation and insight, they pray for the clients and be spiritually guided concerning the issue brought to them.

Also, a pastoral counsellor must be able to maintain confidentiality just like any counsellor ought to inculcate as etiquette. Craig (2011) opined that it is the role of a pastoral counsellor to provide a sense of hope and trust to the patient or client, this makes people to have trust in the capability and strength of the counsellor in carrying out his duty as a counsellor. A counsellor who does not have a sense of confidentiality is not a trustworthy counsellor and can complicate matters for the patient rather than solving the situation on ground.

More also, empathy on the part of the counsellor is essential to rightly dispose the duties towards a client. As expressed by Odeleye (2022), in this case, empathy is not literally putting one's self in the shoes of the fellow in a complicated situation (this is because not all situation could be properly assumed or imagined) but it is the ability of a counsellor to be able to bear

with the counsellee. The counsellee could be complicated in relating with, and for the counsellor to have the best of him and to maximally manage the situation, there is a need to actually be patient with the fellow regardless of the means of the weakness in expression which could most likely be as a result of the complicated situation such person is entangled.

Finally on this note, a personal life of purity is an essential value that a pastoral counsellor should possess. A pastoral counsellor without a good report in the home and society will less likely have people, whose marriage is in disarray, come to him for counselling or admonition. Such counsellor must possess attributes that are enviable to life and that are related to the Christian virtues which he portrays himself to be a proponent towards. This boils down to the moral conduct and presentation of the lifestyle of a pastoral counsellor which must be sanctimonious and enviable in the society.

Biblical Position on Marriage

The Bible is not silent about the matters about marriage as an institution and this is seen both in the Old Testament and the New Testament owing to the fact that, marriage is a great determinant for the sustainability of the race of man on earth and the progressive existence of humanity. Marriage is an institution that is as old as the times in the Garden of Eden. From the time of creation, there was the plan for God to create for man, a woman who will be his companion and help meet. This was eventually made a reality in Genesis 2:18-22. As such, the initial establishment of marriage is that man and woman live in harmony and to serve complementary roles for each other.

Marriage according to Tolorunleke (2008), should be an atmosphere of excitement and a beautiful adventure which should exist between husband and wife. Marriage and the beauty therein as expressed by Toloruleke (2008) do not imply that there will not be tough times, but marriage in the real sense gives room for offences, which appears to be inevitable in life and there should also be room for forgiveness by the couples in such a way that the offences are forgiven and made to be a stepping stone to higher joy and happiness leading to fulfillment for the couples. According to the definition of Ampitan (2012), God is the source of marriage and it was not originated from neither culture nor tradition as such, marriage is an institution which have the union of a man and a woman. Marriage is an ordination made available by God for mankind to cohabit together in love and in unity of existence.

The biblical perception to marriage is therefore to create room for companionship, abstaining from sexual immorality and for procreation. The biblical perception as obviously taught by Odhiambo, Onyango and Maito (2013) establish that, marriage is ordained by God to be union of one man and one woman. The purposes of marriage is further confirmed from the content of Genesis 2:15-25 and Genesis 1:28 which talks about a one man, husband and one woman, wife with further directive of being fruitful through procreation. The three clearly opined further that a godly and biblical marriage shows the kind of relationship between Christ and the church as contained in Ephesians 5:15-25.

Man and woman in marriage are to serve the purpose of companionship for one another (Stott, 1999). They both are intended from the biblical stance to play complementary roles for each other. This is simply because, the loneliness for man in the first place implies incompleteness

and bringing in a woman to live with him in sanctified matrimony is a practice that is meant to last their lifetime as far as both parties are alive. This position is highly held because, the human nature is a jealous type that finds it difficult to give room for multiple “sharing” of a spouse. And such could create complications in the relationship and thereby lead to either party moving the motion for divorce, a motion that is clearly stated by the Bible that God hates (Malachi 2:16).

The contemporary times have seen many forms of marriages which are against the heterosexual form of marriage ordained by the scriptures. Some of these ungodly marriages are gay marriage (homosexuals), lesbianism, bestialism, among others which ranges from getting marriage to same sex to the extent of getting married to animals. Any form of marriage outside a heterogeneous marriage between a man and a woman is not biblically approved.

Marital Conflicts and Divorce in the 21st century Nigeria

Marriage in the 21st century is almost a shadow of its intended purpose of creation. Tolorunleke (2014) strongly posits that there are multiple factors that stand to affect the sustainability of marriage as it starts from simple challenges and arises to complications in the home. This challenges boomerangs because, both parties who have agreed to live together as husband and wife tend to have forgotten or trivialised the fact that there will be differences and continuous adjustments to suit each other and to carry out their roles as couples. Below are some of the major factors leading to divorce in contemporary marriages;

Divorce in the 21st century could be caused by marital infidelity by either of the couple or both. Marital vows made covers fidelity in marriage and this can help the health safety of both parties involved in a marriage. But indulging in martially infidelity poses serious threat to the sustainability of such marriage as mistrust will be built and fear of contracting sexually transmitted diseases will automatically be built. These actions could be cause by the inability of one party to satisfy the other party sexually and it could be as a result of covetousness of the part of the guilty side. Tolorunleke (2014) opine strongly that conflict could evolve when either party fails to satisfy the other party sexually.

Tolorunleke (2014) discovered that marital conflict which can by extension lead to divorce in marriage could be caused by social, economic and physical factors. She also opined that, when the family head is unable to economically and socially meet the needs of the family, conflict can evolve as a result. It implies that, the family is sensitive to meeting individual needs both physically and emotionally.

Some marriages in contemporary times could be shattered by educational imbalance or social imbalance of either party and inability of both to adjust their extremes to relate with one another in the home and in the society. The well-educated party tends to always feel embarrassed by the conduct of the other party who is less educated and it appears as if such fellow cannot be presented in the society. Therefore, rather than to keep up with such imbalance they chose to divorce and go separate ways.

As it had been clearly opined from the biblical point of view, Odhiambo, Onyango and Maito (2013) indicated that a true biblical marriage signifies the relationship between Christ and the church, a kind of affiliation that cannot be broken by challenges. As such, divorce is not an

option in the relationship of Christ with the church as it holds the idea of oneness which should also be the similar situation in man and woman marital affinity.

Pastoral Counseling as Panacea For Divorce

The situation of divorce in the society in contemporary times call for immediate action and rescue in order to preserve the sanctimony of marriages and as such, the various counselling methods are adopted and will be discussed in light of rescuing marriage from divorce in the 21st century Nigeria setting;

The first means to be applied is to listen and pay attention to the client when the counselling session resumes. Young, Griffith and Williams (2003) had rightly expressed that paying attention to the actual situation by mainly listening, showing support and care, then counsel and hearing them out, will go a long way to help the situation brought about by the clients. This implies that, if pastoral counsellors pay attention, it will aid in how to show care to couples and that will aid in how to counsel them too. This position presents that there is no complex situation that is beyond fixing and if a listening ear is given to the couples whose marriage is a dwindling state, divorce can be avoided in order to rescue the marriage from crashing.

Another mode to be applied is the building of trust and confidence in the mind of the concerned persons. People need to feel loved sincerely and not to be judgmental about them, they feel safe sharing their secrets and life with people who would encourage them, instead of condemning them out rightly (Young, Griffith and Williams, 2003). When couples that are facing tough time or couples that are almost at the verge of entering into complicated situations in their families see someone that could be trusted, they tend to open up and be sincere with them. At this point, there is a level of trust and confidence which the pastoral counsellor has built between the couple and himself. This will aid in meddling and rescuing a marriage. As a matter of emphasis, pastoral counsellors should be close to couples ahead of time, this is because, some people find it difficult to open up to people when they are already in a tough situation, but they rather open to someone who have won their trust before such tough time and situation arises.

Furthermore, pastoral counselling should be centered on a discussion to please God rather than only gratifying human's immediate desires. The pastoral counsellor should establish to the couples having challenges in their marriage on a mutual cohabitation to please God. Young, Griffith and Williams (2003) expressed that, the discussion should lead to a more authentic relationship with God. Couples are therefore to substitute and replace wrong thoughts with a positive mental attitude and expression in order to sustain their home. Often times, couples feel other people will be better than their spouse and that is the need and push for aiming towards divorce in order to get a better alternative, but the truth is that there is no perfect being as everyone has one deficiency or the other. This implies that, counsellors are to lay emphasis on the complications of human nature and the need for the couples to adjust and amend their excesses in order to have a proper relationship and a progressive family.

In addition, pastoral counsellors are to get involved from the basis of the relationships of young ones which has a prospect of leading to marriage. They are to win their heart and confidence in a way that the young ones feel safe to share their situations with such counsellor through premarital counselling. Many marriages which were shattered within a short time are marriages

which had foundational problem like logical incompatibility or imbalance based on financial situation of the intended couples or families, educational imbalance of either party, religious affiliations, or tribal identity which is not well dealt with before hopping into marriage. As such, a pastoral counsellor will have been able to address some of the issues which will enlighten the individuals on making the decision to proceed with such marriage or to disembark for that marriage to be instituted.

Lastly on this note, pastoral counsellors are to proffer therapeutic solutions in situations where it becomes necessary to do so. This paper posits that, indeed some situations that are threatening the marriage of individuals could be as a result of mental shortcomings and complications. Some misbehaviours are due failure on the part of the husband to provide economically for the family or for either couple to meet the sexual need of each other (Tolorunleke, 2014). Odeleye (2022) expressed that the strength of a pastoral counsellor is the ability to realise boundaries of his discipline and profession as such, the counsellor is to have in mind that counselling could succeed or be a step to success which could be achieved by referring a client to other quarters (discipline) as the case could be in each specific case. In such cases which are not based on spiritual inclinations, a pastoral counsellor should refer the couple to those who major in such field. For example, a sexually inactive person could be referred to a health nutritionist who could advice on types of food and treatment to be used, while those with mental situation could be referred to the psychiatrist for proper attention before it goes out of hand (Young, Griffith and Williams, 2003). This referral method will further help in establishing a relationship between people of other professions and careers. This can lead to achieving the expected goal in a right way and this should be the joy of any counsellor.

Conclusion

Divorce is never in the plan of God in the marital affairs of men, his plan for man is simply to run a family till a natural death serve the purpose of separation. But considering the current tide and trend in the modern age, there is a call for serious attention from various quarters who are seen to have agitated for divorce or temporary separation as discussed in the course of this paper.

The need therefore arises for a rescue mission to be embarked upon by the church and this could simply be achieved intentionally by the pastoral counsellors who are saddled with the role of both spiritual and psychotherapy tasks to assist in family and marital stability. The pastoral counsellors are simply to be well trained and well groomed to meet marital needs of the society which is one of the most pressing is the malady of divorce. This paper has therefore proffered means and method by which pastoral counsellors can curb or drastically reduced the rampant nature of divorce in the 21st century which will in return rescue and establish the biblical position towards stability in marriage.

Recommendations

In direct establishment of some of the positions discussed about pastoral counselling, this paper recommends that:

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- i. Pastoral counsellors should be well trained in both spiritual and psychotherapeutic knowledge in order to have an holistic conduct
 - ii. Intended couples should be encouraged to pass through premarital counselling before they settle down for marriage
 - iii. Couples are to seek assistance of pastoral counsellors when the going gets tough in their marriage
 - iv. Referral in case of complicated factors should be intentionally adopted by pastoral counsellors as procedure to rescuing marital complications

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